

Quantum Entropy, Degeneracy and Isotropy

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Classically there seems to be the sense of an isotropy in space and time and so statistically this becomes linked with degeneracies, say in a classical gas in space with no potential. Quantum mechanics of a free particle, however, suggests that different momenta, which represent physically different impulses in space, are not associated locally with isotropy in space or time. There is a wavelength in space and period in time (\hbar/p , \hbar/E where $E=pp/2m$ nonrelativistically) and probabilities apply to these regions. We have argued that in general one might associate an entropy in both space and time due to the probabilities within a wavelength/period although generally in the literature this does not seem to be done.

We have also argued previously that the quantum free particle wavelength and period follow from degeneracy associated with the Lorentz invariant: $A = -Et+px$. Here we point out that there is an added degeneracy, namely the direction of p in space. Thus the probabilistic $\exp(ipx)$ associated with a constant momentum can be further associated with various probability distributions in space if the free particle interacts with an n -slit system. In such a case, the particle has a fixed p and direction approaching the slit, but locally there is no spatial isotropy. This local probabilistic feature converts into a probability distribution for different p vector directions creating a unique spatial distribution on a screen when many identical particles, each with the same p , interact with the n -slit system. Each particle, however, begins with a specific p vector and after the interaction has the same magnitude of p , only a different direction. The local anisotropy associated with the wavelength is now converted into a more global spatial distribution due to extra uncertainties associated with impulse hits with the n -slit system. As a result, what one sees as entropy due to an interaction with a n -slit system is associated with degeneracy and the bias to believing that a free particle behaves in a deterministic manner at length scales of the order of a wavelength.

Tossing a Coin or Rolling a Die

One usually thinks of tossing a coin or rolling a die as being probabilistic because one may have different outcomes. These outcomes, however, seem to be symbolic because without markings, a coin has a two-fold degeneracy and a die a six-fold. It is only the labels (and associations assigned to these labels) which make the outcomes seem non-degenerate. One may also note the isotropy associated with the degeneracy.

Quantum Free Particle and Spatial/Temporal Isotropy

It seems that isotropy tends to be associated with space and time. A free particle with momentum p and energy $E=pp/2m$ (nonrelativistically) is not assumed to disrupt space/time. Quantum mechanics, however, shows a marked anisotropy due to $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ i.e. the period and wavelength, but this disruption is only within the time period or wavelength and so is often ignored. There exists probability distributions within a period and wavelength associated

with the mechanical properties of E and p . We have suggested in previous notes that these follow from the Lorentz invariant:

$$A = -Et + px \quad ((1))$$

A also happens to be the nonrelativistic and relativistic classical action if $v=x/t$. There exists a degeneracy in the value of A because $t+\text{constant}/E$ and $x+\text{constant}/p$ yield the same value of A . This degeneracy, we suggest, gives rise to the ideas of $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ which are eigenfunctions of the operators id/dt and $-i\text{id}/dx$. Thus degeneracy leads to probability, but in this case (unlike the coin or die) there is no isotropy.

There is also an extra degeneracy in ((1)) due to the arbitrariness of the vector p . One might thus anticipate that this degeneracy might become linked with $\exp(ipx)$ and create even more anisotropy in space. We suggest that this is what occurs for an interaction with a n -slit system.

N-Slit System Interaction

A quantum free particle has anisotropy in space and time associated with $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-iEt)$, which are two dimensional probabilities. We suggest that in the case of space, the extra degeneracy in the direction of p , may yield further anisotropy in space when an interaction with an n -slit device occurs. We argue that the extra directional degeneracy is linked to $\exp(ipx)$ because the separations of slits must be of the order of \hbar/p for an interference pattern to occur. Each n -slit device gives rise to a specific probability distribution created at the wavelength (two dimensional probability) level by adding “ $\exp(ipx)$ ” (addition of probability for an OR case) for each possible path through the different n slits. (In general, one writes one $\exp(ipx)$ type term for each slit.) The spatial anisotropy together with the uncertainty due to the multiple slits gives rise to an even larger spatial anisotropy because there is a fixed probability distribution for the direction of p . This probability distribution which leads to the interference pattern seen on a screen may at first seem surprising, but we argue it is based on the bias of considering space to be isotropic to a particle with fixed p . Locally (at the wavelength level) it is not and this can give rise to more pronounced spatial anisotropy in certain interactions. From a single particle point of view, the particle originally has p in a certain direction before interacting with the n -slit system and a p with a different direction afterwards. For a single particle there is no sense of extra disorder or deterioration which is sometimes associated with entropy. There is, however, a loss of information to the observer who originally knows both the magnitude and direction of p , and only knows the magnitude after the n -slit interaction. A measurement on a screen determines the direction of p , but this measurement captures the particle.

One considers a stream of identical particles to create an entropy after interacting with an n -slit system because one considers space to be isotropic, with various targets placed at different locations, but ignores the anisotropy and probability built-in to the initial particle.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that there seems to be a tendency to consider space and time as isotropic. We argue, however, that a quantum free particle with energy E and momentum p

breaks this isotropy at least locally within a period \hbar/E and wavelength \hbar/p . We suggest this breaking of temporal and spatial isotropy is due to the degeneracy of the Lorentz invariant (and classical relativistic/nonrelativistic action for $v=x/t$), $A = -Et + px$. This gives rise to the probabilistic picture of $\exp(-iEt)$, $\exp(ipx)$ directly associated with the breaking of time/space isotropy.

We point out that there is an extra degeneracy in space, namely the direction of the vector p which may manifest itself. In fact, for an n -slit interaction, the probabilistic anisotropy of $\exp(ipx)$ couples with OR probabilities for passing through different slits and leads to a probability distribution for the direction of p which manifests itself in an interference pattern on a screen. This pattern may be used to calculate a spatial entropy using Shannon's entropy formula.

We suggest, however, a particle has a p and a direction before and after the interaction. Thus, the entropy is not due to disorder or deterioration, but rather to a loss of information about the direction of p . The free quantum particle already contains a probabilistic anisotropy linked with $\exp(ipx)$ and there is an added degree of freedom associated with the direction of p , so the interference pattern is only surprising if one ignores this built-in free particle spatial anisotropy. In a sense, the n -slit device amplifies the anisotropic probability feature associated with $\exp(ipx)$.